

The Evaluation of Enhancement Competency Policy through Diklat Berjenjang for Early Childhood Teachers

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ABSTRACT: It is important to evaluate the policies that have been rolled out. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the policy of increasing competence through the Diklat Berjenjang project for early childhood education (ECE) teachers in the first five years of policy implementation carried out by the unit (directorate) in the Indonesian government that handles early childhood education teachers and education personnel. Respondents in this study were leaders and staff in related units, leaders and members of ECE partner organizations, officials in charge of ECE in the province, and several principals of ECE schools/institutions. This policy research uses qualitative methods supported by quantitative methods, with a program evaluation approach that is sharpened by a retrospective process formal evaluation approach when analyzing the stages of policy formulation, implementation, and control as well as a goal-free evaluation approach to identify policy impacts. This study found that the directorate took the steps of formulation, implementation, performance evaluation, and policy revision. Empowering the participation of partner organizations is an important component. Diklat Berjenjang project can be a movement to improve the competence of ECE teachers. Norms, procedures, criteria, and standards can be used as a reference. The directorate has not yet coordinated institutionally with educational institutions at the regional level, causing a lack of control over the implementation of education and training. The recommendation of this research is to continue the policy by coordinating with educational institutions or institutions that have the authority to develop Early Childhood Education (ECE) teachers at the regional and central levels.

KEYWORDS: Policy Evaluation, Diklat Berjenjang project, Early Childhood Teachers

I. INTRODUCTION

Mastery of competence is one of the requirements that must be possessed by a teacher in addition to qualifications. Competence is inherent in the teacher and is manifested in quotes, actions and attitudes. To carry out a task, competence must be in accordance with the task requested. This is where a correlation is needed between the tasks carried out with the competency standards that must be attached to an educator. Efforts to increase competence can be done through education and training.

As a program, Early Childhood Education (ECE) is part of the government's and community's efforts to prepare children to socialize and be able to follow the next level of education. Growth and development is a processes experienced by children. With that, there is a trace that will affect the potential of the child in the future. ECE teachers to be able to provide stimulation in the growth and development of children. This demand is contained in regulations in Indonesia that must be met by a ECE teacher. Regulations governing ECE standards nationally.

Community participation and awareness of the importance of early education are getting better. The practice of implementing ECE in the community is increasing. This requires attention to the components of ECE

implementation, including ECE teachers who have competence in accordance with the standards set out in the regulations. At the beginning of the existence of ECE in Indonesia, not all ECE teachers had the required qualifications and competencies. To meet the needs of this community, the government makes policies to improve the competence of ECE teachers according to the competency standards contained in the regulations. One of the policies to improve the competence of ECE teachers is Tiered Education for ECE teachers. *Diklat Berjenjang project* is an educational and training activity that is carried out in stages for ECE teachers. The levels include *Diklat Berjenjang project* basic level, advanced level, and advanced level. The *Diklat Berjenjang* referred to in this study is the basic level of *Diklat Berjenjang* conducted outside the network. At that time, this policy was contained in the regulation, namely the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 36 of 2010 concerning the Organization and Work Procedure of the Ministry of National Education and was clarified in the Appendix to the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 2 of 2010 concerning the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of National Education for 2010-2014. Until 2022, *Diklat Berjenjang* is still being followed by ECE teachers. Even at the beginning of the Pandemic, an online-based *Diklat Berjenjang* was initiated that utilizes an LMS (learning management system). Until now, competency improvement through online (in-network) or offline-based Training and Education is still being carried out.

The policy of increasing competence through *Diklat Berjenjang* for ECE teachers was introduced to the public in 2011. At that time, several things that happened in the community could be noted related to increasing the competence of ECE teachers, including the non-fulfillment of ECE teacher standards at the Pembina State Kindergarten of Ende Regency. need to be given ECE teacher training (Anamara, 2013: 210-216). Another problem related to *Diklat Berjenjang* is that the recruitment of participants is not entirely in accordance with the criteria contained in the guidelines for the implementation of *Diklat Berjenjang* and aspects of post-training monitoring and evaluation services have not been carried out properly due to the limited area of participants and monitoring officers (Riza, 2012: 149 -151). It is important to evaluate the competency improvement policy through 'Graduated Education' for ECE Teachers which has been implemented for five years since the introduction of this policy.

II. METHOD

The source of data referred to in this study is related to policy information, consisting of 3 elements, namely places, actors, and activities (Sugiono, 2009: 389). The place where the policy is formulated so that information on the impact of the policy is obtained. Actors are people who are involved in the policy process. Meanwhile, activities are activities carried out in the context of implementing the *Diklat Berjenjang* policy which is manifested in documents, data, and information.

The data collection procedure uses interviews, document analysis/study, observation, questionnaires/questionnaires, and triangulation (Sugiono, 2009: 423). Data analysis procedures include qualitative and quantitative data analysis. Qualitative data analysis to determine the accuracy of the research focus; formulate follow-up strategies; and formulate conclusions and provisional findings (Putra, 2013: 75). The quantitative data of this study were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Data analysis with descriptive statistics is presented in the form of tables or graphs about the aspects measured in the evaluation. Actual decision-making at each evaluation stage is carried out by measuring at each component stage which is summarized in the table. This table shows the effects of comparison between objective standards in the form of pre-defined criteria and actual recording results in the field. The comparison produces a conclusion effect in the form of a decision on each component.

The policy evaluation model of this research design is inspired by Wollmann's notion of policy evaluation which focuses on two things, namely policy evaluation as program analysis and policy evaluation as a phase of the policy cycle (2007: 366). Policy evaluation as a program analysis will use components, namely concepts, processes, results/outputs, and impacts. If Akif (Sartika, 2011: 112) uses five components, namely concepts, procedures, results, and impact, then the model in this study fuses procedures into concepts. This is supported by Nugraha (2014: 253) who incorporates legal norms (Akif uses the term procedure) into the policy formulation process. To evaluate the environment, Akif uses impact while this research model uses impact.

According to Ali and Alam impact consists of effect and impact. The effect is a short-term impact that is directly felt related to the policy, while the impact is an indirect impact, felt in the long term (Ali and Alam, 2012: 25).

This policy research uses the program evaluation approach (the program evaluation approach) which is sharpened by a retrospective process formal evaluation approach (Dunn, 2004: 615-616) when analyzing the stages of policy formulation, implementation, and control and uses a goal-free evaluation approach (Fitzpatrick, Sanders, and Worthen, 2002: 84) when identifying impacts. Formal evaluation is an approach that uses descriptive methods to produce valid and reliable policy information on the basis of policy program objectives that have been formally announced by policymakers. While objective-free evaluation is used to measure all impacts that occur in the field, not only on results planned.

Picture 1. Research Model Evaluation of Competency Improvement Policy through Diklat Berjenjang for ECE Teachers

This is to add to the findings of unplanned results or impacts. Facts on the ground are compared with evaluation criteria. This comparison will produce something meaningful in the form of values. The values obtained are the results of studies that will ultimately make recommendations from this research. The researcher named this model the *Illimani Policy Evaluation Model*.

III. DISCUSSION

This policy was born on the community's issue of the need to increase the competence of ECE teachers. This need is based on the lack of availability of teachers in cities and remote areas who have the competence as required in regulations related to ECE standards, a non-standardized training system, the lack of ECE-related majors available at universities, and a culture of improving the competence of ECE teachers who are not yet orderly. The focus of the content of Diklat Berjenjang places the improvement of ECE teacher competence on the basis of the teacher competency standards that are currently in effect, namely Permendiknas number 58 of 2009 concerning ECE Standards and other regulations as a support for the implementation of 'Graduated Education'.

Most of the processes in the policy-making stage have been carried out, namely 1) Determining policy issues in the form of determining policy issues based on conditions, needs, and desires for an increase in ECE teacher competence through standardized education and training; 2) Establish a Policy Formulation Drafting Team. The first team compiled an academic text of ECE teacher competency standards which was the forerunner of the substance of the policy by inviting experts. The second team has focused on the policy on Diklat Berjenjang; 3) Carry out pre-policy preparation tasks through the formulation of academic texts and the formulation of zero policy drafts; 4) The public process is in the form of activity for drafting a manuscript that invites various related elements; 5) Formulating the first final draft in the form of discussion of the draft manuscript as the process of formulating the first final draft; 6) Focus group discussions, preceded by a trial draft of the manuscript followed by focus group discussions; 7) Formulate the second final draft through the finalization of the manuscript; 8) Ratification/legalization in the form of signing the guidelines in 2012 and the revised text in 2013.

Most of the legal aspects of competency improvement policies through Diklat Berjenjang follow the existing regulatory levels. Norms which are government administration rules are complemented by standards as references/benchmarks and procedures as methods or procedures for implementation. As a measure of performance, the criteria are set in the norms made. Policies that are outlined in programs and activities are contained in the form of guidelines, technical instructions for the implementation of face-to-face training, and independent assignments. In relation to the legality of the cooperation, a cooperation agreement has been made with supporting documents in the form of proposal submission and a Decree (SK) determining the recipient of assistance for the implementation of Diklat Berjenjang. The policy binds ECE teachers as a norm to improve their competence and binds participants if they do not follow the training rules, namely they are not entitled to the relevant training certificate.

The results of the evaluation of policy implementation show that in carrying out the policy, each individual knows his/her duties and works in accordance with the task description contained in the decree, design, and direction of the leadership. Internal coordination has been carried out with fellow units (sub-directorates) and other directorates that also handle ECE institutions, namely the Directorate of Early Childhood Education Development (PPAUD); very effective external coordination with partner organizations, effective coordination with Limited Liability Companies, less effective coordination with the Regional education Offices and UPT PAUDNI/BPKB (the technical implementing unit for ECE programs and community education at the regional/provincial level). There is a policy strategy contained in programs and activities that mutually support the Diklat Berjenjang policy in the form of policy text formulation, socialization, preparation of trainers, distribution of aid funds, synchronization, mentoring, review, and monitoring and evaluation related to Diklat Berjenjang. The above conditions affect the performance of the training provider in conducting Diklat Berjenjang.

The policy control process includes aspects of monitoring results, performance results, and results from maintenance activities through the policy revision process. Monitoring as part of control activities is carried out from the early stages of policy implementation through synchronization activities until the end of the 'Graduated Education' activity, namely review activities. This process provides data. The data is stored in the person in charge of activities in the current year and is in archive storage after the current year.

The directorate's performance in the implementation process is perceived as good by the training provider as the education and training provider and has an effect on the performance of training providers, educational institutions, and training targets. In terms of the target of the State Budget program, the achievement of the Diklat Berjenjang exceeded the target (125%). This is because training providers who receive state budget assistance funds maximize funds through a budget sharing system. Efforts made by the government and training providers are able to awaken ECE teachers to increase their competence through independent training. However, there has not been much support for the Diklat Berjenjang mentoring program in the regions by educational institutions. The existing program is the distribution of APBD program funds in 10 provinces to improve the competence of ECE teachers.

The Diklat Berjenjang policy is revised every year in order to improve parts that are not yet perfect or align with current conditions. Policy revisions are implemented in the program and reference for the Diklat Berjenjang program. Revisions are made following changes that occur, both changes in regulations and community conditions.

Evaluation of the policy environment. Empirical facts regarding the management of policy concepts have a good impact (80%) on society. The following is a breakdown of the impacts felt by the community:

Picture 2. Impact Evaluation on Policy Concept Management

The suitability of the policy to the needs of the community is very much felt. This illustrates that the policy is considered to be in accordance with the needs, namely efforts to increase the competence of ECE teachers. On the other hand, the support for the concept in the form of providing resource persons and the composition of the curriculum prepared for policy implementation was also perceived as good (71%) by the community. Here are the details:

Picture 3. Impact Evaluation on Concept Support

The picture above shows that the availability of resource persons is only 62%. This is relevant to the data of participants who took part in the Training of Trainers (TOT). When compared to the number of TOT

graduates with the number of training providers which are in the 5:1 position, it means that a Diklat Berjenjang program only has 5 resource persons from post-TOT participants organized by the directorate.

The performance of the directorate in preparing policies was felt very well (83%) by the public. Here are the details in the pictures:

Picture 4. Impact Evaluation on Directorate Performance

The performance directorate in preparing the policy has an indirect impact on policies in the ECE sector, namely 1) the establishment of intensive communication between the leaders of ECE partner organizations and the government, 2) Utilization of the Diklat Berjenjang certificate as part of the assessment of accreditation agencies to meet the standards of teachers and education personnel by the National Accreditation Board for Non-Formal Education, 3) Utilization of the Diklat Berjenjang certificate as one of the requirements for obtaining incentives in education policies in several regions, 4) the use of the Diklat Berjenjang concept for the program to increase the competence of ECE teachers in the program the work of the Word Bank and the Ministry of Villages, 5) Recognition of the results of Diklat Berjenjang as an effort to accelerate qualification improvement in Open University policies, but there are also other impacts that arise, namely 6) lack of coordination with educational institutions or independent institutions causing a lack of excess guarantees the quality of Diklat Berjenjang conducted by government institutions at the regional level

The influence of the policy of increasing competence through Diklat Berjenjang is also felt in educational institutions, education and training providers, and the community. The following is a graph of financial influence based on data in the field:

Picture 5. Financial Effects for Local Education Agencies

Picture 6. Financial Influence on Education and Training Providers

Picture 7. Financial Influence on Training Participants

Picture 8. Financial Effects on Parents

Picture 9. Financial Effects from the Side of Community Groups

Based on Figures 5-9, the most visible financial impact of this policy is the disbursement of APBD funds; the creativity of the organizers to get sponsorship and share the budget; the participation of students to improve their own competence through self-help funds; starting to grow the participation of parents to provide financial support to ECE teachers, and community participation to increase the competence of ECE teachers.

Non-economic influences are also felt due to the policy of increasing competence through Diklat Berjenjang. The following is a graph that reflects the non-economic impact of the competency improvement policy through the Diklat Berjenjang:

Picture 10. Non-economic Effects on Educational Agencies

Picture 11. Non-economic Effects on Education and Training Providers

Picture 12. Non-economic Effects on Training Participants

Figure 13. Non-economic Effects on Parents

Picture 14. Non-economic Impact on Society

Based on Graphs 10-14, it can be seen that there are non-economic influences on educational institutions, namely that the community understands policies and prioritizes ECE programs; the more widespread the communication network of the education and training institutions, the more familiar names of

partner organizations(called: Ormit) and the increased managerial capabilities at the partner organizations; ECE teachers know the central policy on ECE, there is an increase in competence, and parents feel that the teacher's attitude is more communicative and the children become better.

The policy of increasing competence brings a change in attitude to the organizers in educational institutions, education and training providers, training participants, and parents. Here the impact is broken down in the graph:

Picture 15. Influence on Changes in Attitudes of Local Educational Institutions

Picture 16. Influence on Changes in Attitudes of Education and Training Organizers

Picture 17. Effect on Changes in Attitudes of Training Participants

Picture 18. Attitude Changes in Parents

Picture 19. Changes in People's Attitudes

The data in Pictures 15-19, reflect a very large influence on changes in the attitude of administrators in educational institutions to carry out supervision; there is commitment and confidence in partner organizations but there is still a sense of dependence on government funds (APBN/APBD); training participants who are ECE teachers are able to teach better and teach friends of the same profession and their performance increases; increasing parental concern for children and educators; and increasing public confidence in the quality of ECE teachers.

The policy concept that contains norms, standards, procedures, and criteria has a direct impact on stakeholders, namely the understanding of objectives, ideas, and procedures so that they can be carried out in accordance with the expectations of making policies. Policy support in the form of the availability of a standardized curriculum is very helpful in the policy implementation process. The curriculum in the training will guide the implementation process in the field. In terms of the number of resource persons, it has not been able to meet the needs ideally. In certain regions/provinces with minimal resource persons, they must bring in from other regions. A clear policy concept also has an impact on the emergence of new policies that support efforts to increase competence. The detailed policy concept is able to be responded to by stakeholders and utilized according to the similarities in the intended policy aspect.

The policy formulation process and continued coordination at the implementation stage involving related parties such as other directorates that handle ECE institutions (Direktorat PPAUD), partner organizations, academics from universities, and tutors from UPT PAUDNI are able to make policies that are recognized by these parties. Accompanied by a strategy in the form of programs that support the implementation of policies such as distribution of social assistance funds, synchronization, and assistance in making policies that are understandable by stakeholders, especially those who participate in these supporting programs. The quality of the training provider is considered good. They are able to identify and implement policies as well as mobilize the community to participate in independent training with self-help funds from participants or seek Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) funds. Independent education and training carried out independently by the community have resulted in 138% more participants than the training carried out by the government. The overall education and training recorded at the directorate were recorded at 21.88% when compared to the number of teachers recorded in the data on the Unique Number of Teachers and Education Personnel. Based on the target of the Mid-Term Development Plan of the Direktorat PTK PAUDNI development 2010-2014, the percentage of Activity Performance Indicators (IKK) for ECE teachers who participated in technical training was 31%. When compared with the achievement, the Diklat Berjenjang accounted for 21.88% of the achievement of ECE teacher training until 2014. This indicates that the Diklat Berjenjang policy is able to boost the achievement of the IKK targets.

These quantitative achievements have an impact on the quality of life and better attitudes of ECE teachers, parents, and students, as well as the community. Management, coordination, and strategy in policy implementation, in addition to influencing the achievement of results, also have an impact on increasing the quality of partner organizations in carrying out education and training and expanding communication networks and networks. The impact that was also found from this strategy was the dependence on aid funds to carry out activities in several partner organizations. This can also be explained by the research data which identified that insufficient financial factors were an internal obstacle faced by community organizations (partners) to participate in government programs. (Durado, 2016). Another impact found is the lack of coordination with educational institutions at the leadership level in the regions as part of policy instruments. The impact is that

there is no coaching and quality assurance program for the implementation of Diklat Berjenjang by regional institutions.

Based on the discussion above, the decision on the criteria for field findings and the values generated as part of the implications for concept or scientific development are:

Table 1. The Resulting Criteria and Value Decisions

ASPECT	DECISION CRITERIA	VALUES
Content Focus	Very good	The fulfillment of ECE teacher standards is a concept developed in the ECE Teacher Diklat Berjenjang policy
Process	Well	Steps that are traceable and complete by involving all relevant parties to maximize policies are responded to by all stakeholders
Legality	Well	A clear and systematic legality aspect is needed so that the policy can run well
Personal Management	Very good	The effectiveness of personal management occurs because every person involved in the policy works in accordance with the details of the tasks contained in the written documents and directives from the leadership
Coordination	Well	The effectiveness of coordination between the central government and partner organizations is able to awaken and mobilize ECE teachers to improve their competence, but it is not perfect because it has not been supported by effective coordination with educational institutions at the provincial/district/city level.
Strategy	Well	The effectiveness of the strategies contained in programs and activities will be able to facilitate policies to be accepted by stakeholders.
Monitoring	Well	Monitoring carried out from the beginning to the end of policy implementation produces complete data.
Performance evaluation	Well	Community participation is able to mobilize awareness of increasing the competence of ECE teachers but needs to be supported by mentoring and control programs by authorized institutions in the regions
Maintenance/ Revision	Well	Maintenance/policy revisions based on field data/findings are carried out as part of policy control activities so that they can run according to their objectives.
Management policy)	Well	The concept of education and training to increase the competence of standardized ECE teachers can still be recognized by the community, even with the lack of support for external mentoring and quality assurance programs or educational institutions in the regions.
Financial	Enough	Financial participation began to grow along with awareness to increase competence which is the responsibility of the teachers themselves, the community, and the government
Quality of Life	Very good	Excellent government policy concepts and strategies are able to have an impact on improving the quality of life (non-economic)
Change of attitude	Very good	Policy concepts and strategies equipped with implementation examples (independent tasks) are able to bring about the activation of community attitudes for the better.

IV. CONCLUSION

The concept of a policy of increasing competence through Diklat Berjenjang for ECE teachers is the government's decision to increase the competence of ECE teachers through training held in stages. The Diklat Berjenjang for ECE teachers can be carried out by partner organizations and/or training institutions/certain work units by referring to the established reference. Legally, the policy of increasing competence through Diklat

Berjenjang is stated in the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture but the concept of increasing competence needs to be supported in the main tasks and functions of the directorate.

Policy implementation at the practical level is carried out by partner organizations. The synergy between the directorate and partner organizations is able to make 'Leveled Education' a movement to increase the competence of ECE teachers. On the other hand, this policy has not been optimal in building coordination with a high-quality commitment between partner organizations and/or training institutions/certain work units in the regions in providing guidance and quality assurance of Diklat Berjenjang for ECE teachers;

The policy to increase competence through Diklat Berjenjang until 2014 succeeded in contributing 21.88% of the 31% IKK target for improving the competence of ECE teachers in the medium-term program plan for the current year. This means that 9.12% can be met by other competency improvement policies that are not 'tiered training';

The Diklat Berjenjang policy has an impact in the form of: a) the presence of new policies that support efforts to increase the competence of ECE teachers, including the use of a Diklat Berjenjang certificate as part of the institutional accreditation assessment by the National Accreditation Board for Non-formal Education (BAN PNF), the use of certificates 'Tiered Education' as one of the requirements for obtaining incentives in regional education policies, the use of the Diklat Berjenjang concept for the ECE teacher competency improvement program in The World Bank and Ministry of Village work programs, recognition of the results of Diklat Berjenjang as an effort to accelerate the improvement of qualifications in University policies Open in Indonesia; b) starting to grow financial participation from the community to improve self-competence; c) excellent quality of life improvement includes: central government policies, especially the existence of ECE being better known to the community, prioritizing the ECE program, establishing more inter-institutional and personal communication networks, increasing the competence of ECE teachers, changing students for the better, and more people who care about the ECE program. and d) a very good attitude changes in the form of increased supervision of educational institutions as well as increased commitment and confidence of organizers but there is still a sense of dependence on government funds (APBD/APBN), the performance of training participants increases, teachers teach better and are willing to teach their peers, people parents/community care more about teachers and children, and ECE institutions are more trusted.

The limitation of this study is that changes in the nomenclature of institutions cannot be avoided due to changes in regulations that existed during this research.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The legislature as the maker of the formulation of laws (legislative rights) to change in the form of adding strengthening of the policy concept of increasing competence in the duties and functions of institutions that handle teachers and education personnel. Consistently pays attention to budgeting (budget rights) that support community efforts to play a role in increasing the competence of ECE teachers.
2. For the central government in charge of teachers and education staff, improve coordination with a high-quality commitment so that the policy formulations that have been determined can be implemented properly and produce the expected goals and have a positive impact on ECE teachers. Institutional coordination with institutions responsible for education or independent institutions that have authority in the field of teaching ECE teachers at the regional and central levels is accompanied by improvement of the quality assurance system through the implementation of programs that are committed to quality.
3. For local governments, it is necessary to increase resource support for quality development and expansion of ECE access, which is accompanied by an excellent and responsive working paradigm in accordance with community needs. Furthermore, this is translated into sustainable programs that refer to national policies.
4. Universities, especially the Institute for Teachers and Education Personnel, are expected to be able to provide support for academic studies that can strengthen the scientific side of material directed at improving the quality and professionalism of ECE teachers at both the central and regional levels. Analytical studies of academic elements are also needed when formulating concepts related to policies to increase the competence of ECE teachers.

5. ECE teachers and the community: both individually and in groups, it is necessary to continuously improve the competence, experience, and insight needed to be able to carry out their duties professionally. This is in line with the increasing development of science and technology and the demands of the community for quality education needs.

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